

AN ELEMENTARY OPPOSITE-PAIR PROOF FOR THREE EXCEPTIONAL REGULAR POLYGONAL RATIONAL-DISTANCE CASES

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ABSTRACT. For a regular polygon with rational side length, consider the all-vertices rational-distance problem: whether there exists a point in the plane whose distances to all vertices are rational. Barbara's early treatment of the unit regular polygon problem left the values $n = 8, 12, 24$ as exceptional possibilities among $n \geq 7$, while the square case $n = 4$ is the classical four-distance problem. This note records a short, self-contained proof excluding the three exceptional values 8, 12, 24. The argument uses only opposite vertex pairs, distance-square differences, and the irrationality of $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$. The note is not presented as a solution of an open problem; rather, it isolates a particularly elementary mechanism behind these exceptional cases and contrasts it with the square case, where no comparable irrational-direction obstruction is available.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let $\mathcal{R}_n(s)$ denote a regular n -gon in the Euclidean plane with side length $s > 0$. We say that $\mathcal{R}_n(s)$ has an all-vertices rational-distance point if there exists $P \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that

$$|P - A| \in \mathbb{Q}$$

for every vertex A of $\mathcal{R}_n(s)$. In this note s is assumed rational. Since scaling by a non-zero rational number preserves rationality of all distances, it is enough to consider the unit case $s = 1$.

The case $n = 4$ is the classical four-distance problem for the unit square: whether there exists a point in the plane, or in the interior depending on the chosen formulation, at rational distances from all four vertices. This problem remains open; see Guy's Problem D19 and Berry's survey-style treatment [3, 5].

Barbara's 2009 paper [1] studied the unit regular polygon problem and proved a negative result in almost all cases; in that treatment, the remaining exceptional values for $n \geq 7$ were

$$n \in \{8, 12, 24\}.$$

Barbara's later *Mathematical Gazette* note [2] gives a subsequent published treatment of the polygonal rational-distance problem, and Meskhishvili independently treated the case $n = 24$ in [6]. Thus the purpose of the present note is modest: it gives a short elementary exclusion of $n = 8, 12, 24$ and makes explicit why these cases do not share the same arithmetic difficulty as the square.

The proof is stronger than an interior-point exclusion. For $n = 8, 12, 24$ it rules out rational-distance points anywhere in the plane.

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2. THE OPPOSITE-PAIR OBSERVATION

Place a regular polygon with centre at the origin. If its circumradius is R , then opposite vertices have the form Ru and $-Ru$, where u is a unit vector.

Lemma 1 (Opposite-pair rationality). *Let $R > 0$, let $u \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be a unit vector, and let $P = (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. If*

$$|P - Ru|, |P + Ru| \in \mathbb{Q},$$

then

$$R(P \cdot u) \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Proof. Both squared distances are rational, so their difference is rational. Expanding gives

$$\begin{aligned} |P - Ru|^2 - |P + Ru|^2 &= (P - Ru) \cdot (P - Ru) - (P + Ru) \cdot (P + Ru) \\ &= -4R(P \cdot u). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $R(P \cdot u) \in \mathbb{Q}$. □

3. THE OCTAGON

Proposition 2. *A regular octagon with rational side length has no point in the plane at rational distances from all eight vertices.*

Proof. By rational rescaling, assume that the side length is 1. Place the octagon with centre at the origin and circumradius

$$R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/8)}.$$

Rotate the octagon so that it has opposite vertex directions

$$(1, 0), \quad (0, 1), \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1, 1), \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(-1, 1).$$

Let $P = (x, y)$ be an all-vertices rational-distance point. Applying Lemma 1 to the first two directions gives

$$Rx \in \mathbb{Q}, \quad Ry \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Put

$$A = Rx, \quad B = Ry.$$

Then $A, B \in \mathbb{Q}$. Applying Lemma 1 to the directions $(1, 1)/\sqrt{2}$ and $(-1, 1)/\sqrt{2}$ gives

$$\frac{A + B}{\sqrt{2}} \in \mathbb{Q}, \quad \frac{-A + B}{\sqrt{2}} \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since $A + B$ and $-A + B$ are rational and $\sqrt{2}$ is irrational, these two conditions force

$$A + B = 0, \quad -A + B = 0.$$

Thus $A = B = 0$, and therefore $P = (0, 0)$.

So the only possible all-vertices rational-distance point is the centre. But the centre-to-vertex distance is R . Since

$$\sin^2(\pi/8) = \frac{2 - \sqrt{2}}{4},$$

we have

$$R^2 = \frac{1}{4 \sin^2(\pi/8)} = \frac{1}{2 - \sqrt{2}} = 1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \notin \mathbb{Q}.$$

Hence $R \notin \mathbb{Q}$, so the centre is not a rational-distance point. This contradiction proves the proposition. □

4. THE DODECAGON

Proposition 3. *A regular dodecagon with rational side length has no point in the plane at rational distances from all twelve vertices.*

Proof. Again assume unit side length. Place the dodecagon with centre at the origin and circumradius

$$R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/12)}.$$

After a rotation, the dodecagon has opposite vertex directions

$$(1, 0), \quad (0, 1), \quad \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right), \quad \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\right).$$

Let $P = (x, y)$ be an all-vertices rational-distance point. From the first two directions and Lemma 1,

$$A := Rx \in \mathbb{Q}, \quad B := Ry \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Applying Lemma 1 in the direction $(\sqrt{3}/2, 1/2)$ gives

$$\frac{\sqrt{3}A + B}{2} \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since $A, B \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $\sqrt{3} \notin \mathbb{Q}$, this forces $A = 0$. Applying Lemma 1 in the direction $(1/2, \sqrt{3}/2)$ gives

$$\frac{A + \sqrt{3}B}{2} \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since $A = 0$ and $B \in \mathbb{Q}$, this forces $B = 0$. Hence $P = (0, 0)$.

Thus the only possible point is the centre. But

$$R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/12)} = \frac{1}{2 \sin(15^\circ)} = \frac{\sqrt{6} + \sqrt{2}}{2},$$

which is irrational. Therefore the centre is not a rational-distance point, a contradiction. \square

5. THE REGULAR 24-GON

Proposition 4. *A regular 24-gon with rational side length has no point in the plane at rational distances from all twenty-four vertices.*

Proof. Assume unit side length. After a suitable rotation, the regular 24-gon has opposite vertex directions

$$(1, 0), \quad (0, 1), \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1, 1), \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(-1, 1).$$

These are the same four directions used in the octagon case. Therefore the proof of Proposition 2, using only these four opposite pairs, shows that any all-vertices rational-distance point must be the centre.

The centre-to-vertex distance is

$$R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/24)}.$$

We have

$$\sin^2(\pi/24) = \frac{1 - \cos(\pi/12)}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{6} + \sqrt{2}}{4}\right).$$

The number $\sqrt{6} + \sqrt{2}$ is irrational, since its square is $8 + 4\sqrt{3}$. Hence $\sin^2(\pi/24) \notin \mathbb{Q}$, so $R^2 \notin \mathbb{Q}$ and therefore $R \notin \mathbb{Q}$. Thus the centre is not a rational-distance point, giving a contradiction. \square

6. CONSEQUENCES AND SCOPE

Corollary 5. *The exceptional values $n = 8, 12, 24$ left by Barbara’s 2009 unit-polygon theorem are excluded by the elementary opposite-pair argument above.*

Proof. The values 8, 12, 24 are precisely the three cases treated in Propositions 2, 3, and 4. \square

Corollary 6. *For regular polygons with rational side length, after the known polygonal exclusions and the elementary exclusions above, the only remaining obstruction to the statement*

“only $n = 3$ and $n = 6$ admit all-vertices rational-distance points”

is the square case $n = 4$.

Proof. The case $n = 4$ is exactly the four-distance problem for the square. Barbara’s 2009 result excludes $n = 5$ and all $n \geq 7$ except 8, 12, 24, and Corollary 5 excludes these three remaining values. The cases $n = 3$ and $n = 6$ are positive: rational-distance points for equilateral triangles are classical, and for the unit regular hexagon the centre is at distance 1 from every vertex. \square

Remark 7 (Why the square is different). The mechanism above is unavailable for the square. A square has only the two opposite vertex directions $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$ after rotation. Lemma 1 therefore gives only

$$Rx \in \mathbb{Q}, \quad Ry \in \mathbb{Q},$$

which leaves two rational degrees of freedom and gives no contradiction. The octagon supplies the additional irrational 45° directions, and the dodecagon supplies the additional irrational 30° and 60° directions. These extra directions collapse the point to the centre; the irrational circumradius then rules out the centre itself. This explains, at an elementary level, why the residual square case is genuinely different from the exceptional even cases 8, 12, 24.

Remark 8 (No priority claim). This note should not be read as claiming that $n = 8, 12, 24$ are open. Its purpose is to isolate a short elementary proof of these exclusions and to make explicit the opposite-pair mechanism. The later literature, in particular Barbara’s Mathematical Gazette note [2], should be cited for the subsequent published treatment of the polygonal rational-distance problem; Meskhishvili’s paper [6] also contains an independent treatment of $n = 24$.

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